

Characterization of Ce-doped yttria ceramics prepared by pressure filtration

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Cerium doped yttrium oxide ($Y_2O_3:Ce^{3+}$) nanopowders have been synthesized using precipitation method (1-3) with ammonium hydroxide used as a precipitation agent. The aqueous nitrate solution of Y^{3+} was prepared by dissolving yttria powder (99.99 %) in diluted nitric acid (HNO_3) under continuous stirring at $90^\circ C$ and then diluted into 0.1 M with deionized water. The 0.1M solution of Ce^{3+} was prepared by dissolving cerium nitrate (99.99 %) in deionized water. The mixed metal nitrate solution was dripped into ammonium solution, under continuous rapid stirring, ensuring there was sufficiently high excess of ammonia to eliminate any pH fluctuations throughout the process. The mixed solution turned to opaque white slurry. After 12 h aging the slurry was vacuum filtered through filter paper and the resulting white precipitate was washed with distilled water, dried overnight in air at $100^\circ C$, crushed and ground with pestle in an agate mortar, and calcined in air for 3 h at $700^\circ C$ (heating rate $10^\circ C/min$). Partly agglomerated powders with the primary size of Y_2O_3 nanoparticles ~ 55 nm and cubic crystal structure were prepared. The precipitation method led to severe agglomeration of ceria doped yttria powder. The powder had to be subjected to efficient de-agglomeration before it could be used for preparation of green compacts. The green compacts were prepared by vacuum-pressure filtration of prepared alcoholic suspension and reached relative density above 43 %.

Figure 1 shows the SEM micrograph of synthesized Ce^{3+} -doped Y_2O_3 powders. The powder is agglomerated with the primary particle size of approximately 55 nm, which is in good accord with the X-ray diffraction data. All ceria doped samples show the same particle size and all samples are agglomerated. Doping of yttria powder by ceria did not have any significant effect on particle size and distribution.

Fig 1: SEM micrograph of the synthesised Ce^{3+} -doped Y_2O_3 powder, A) 0.001 mol% Ce, B) 0.005 mol % Ce, C) 0.01 mol % Ce

Fig. 2 Fracture surfaces of Y_2O_3 sintered ceramics prepared from Ce^{3+} doped powders, A) 0.001 mol % Ce, B) 0.005 mol % Ce, C) 0.01 mol % Ce

Figure. 2 shows the fracture surfaces of sintered Ce^{3+} doped yttria ceramics. SEM analysis of all ceria doped materials displayed microstructure with closed porosity, which could be used as starting material for hot isostatic pressing. **Table 1** summarizes the relative densities of all Ce^{3+} doped yttria samples after sintering at 1550 °C.

Table 1: Relative density of Ce^{3+} doped yttria ceramic prepared by pressure filtration method, sintered at 1550°C for 3h.

Ce^{3+} doped yttria	Relative density
0.001 Ce^{3+}	97.88 %
0.005 Ce^{3+}	98.38 %
0.01 Ce^{3+}	98.57 %

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